

Psychological Markers of Stress in the Context of Disease-Prone Behaviour Patterns Among Cebuano Working Adults: A Structural Equation Modelling Approach

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Abstract

This study investigated the structural relationship between disease-prone behavior patterns (DPBP) and psychological stress markers, specifically anxiety, depression, and somatic symptom burden, among Cebuano working adults. Guided by Gabor Maté's concept of stress-related behavioral traits and informed by Filipino indigenous psychology (Sikolohiyang Pilipino), the model examined four latent behavioral constructs: compulsive concern for others' emotional needs, over-identification with responsibilities, suppression of healthy anger, and a perceived duty to regulate others' emotions. A total of 1,134 working adults participated in the study, completing validated self-report measures including the GAD-7, PHQ-2, and SSS-8. Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) using the DWLS estimator showed a well-fitting model ($\chi^2 = 745.478$, $df = 147$, $p < .001$; $CFI = .984$; $TLI = .981$; $RMSEA = .060$; $SRMR = .055$). All four behavioral constructs loaded significantly onto the higher-order DPBP factor, which in turn significantly predicted psychological stress ($\beta = .455$, $p < .001$). These findings suggest that culturally ingrained behaviors, often perceived as virtues such as self-sacrifice, conformity, and emotional suppression, may be risk factors for internalizing psychological distress. The study underscores the importance of context-sensitive psychological models, especially in collectivist cultures like the Philippines, where interpersonal harmony may mask maladaptive stress responses.

Keywords: *Disease-prone behavior Pattern, Psychological Stress Markers, Filipino traits, Structural Equation Modelling.*

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Introduction

The enduring assumption that certain personality traits predispose individuals to various adverse health outcomes has been a long-standing area of scientific inquiry (Conversano & Giuseppe, 2021; Costa et al., 2019; Luo et al., 2022; Roberts et al., 2007; Turiano et al., 2011). This interest intensified in the 1950s with the pioneering research of Friedman and Rosenman, who first identified a link between competitive, time-urgent, and hostile (Type A vs Type B) personality traits and an increased risk of cardiovascular disease. This initial discovery has since been supported by numerous empirical studies linking various personality patterns and the development of cardiovascular disease (Friedman, 2024; Petticrew et al., 2012; Proietti et al., 2011). Building on initial findings, later research identified "Type C" personality,

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marked by passivity, emotion suppression, and conformity, as potentially cancer-prone (Eskelinen & Ollonen, 2011; Rymarczyk et al., 2020; Shen et al., 2021). Similarly, Denollet later identified "Type D" (chronic worry, social inhibition, negative affectivity), which was linked to general distress (Denollet, 2000; Kupper & Denollet, 2018; Mols & Denollet, 2010; Moryś et al., 2015).

However, research into the direct relationship between "personality" and health faced substantial criticism from the scientific community, largely due to its perceived reductionist view of personality (McCrae & Costa, 2003). This prompted researchers to explore other variables that contributed to the development of health problems, taking into account the sociocultural aspects of the individual (Kawachi, 2024; McQueen, 2007; Taukeni, 2019), one of which was disease-prone behavior patterns.

Maté (2022) introduced the concept of Disease-Prone Behavior Patterns (DPBP), which he associated with an increased risk for developing both physical and mental health issues. These patterns include a) compulsive concern for others' emotional needs at the expense of one's own, b) over-identification with duties and responsibilities, c) suppression of healthy anger, and d) a perceived responsibility for others' feelings and an ingrained need to avoid disappointing anyone. According to Maté (2022), these behavior patterns are significantly associated with an increased risk of developing adverse health outcomes, which is also supported by various independent empirical studies. For instance, the suppression of anger has been linked to an increased risk of coronary atherosclerosis (Vella & Friedman, 2009). Over-identification with jobs and responsibilities has been associated with an increased risk of coronary heart disease (Toker et al., 2012), ischemic heart disease (Eller et al., 2009), and emotional exhaustion (Liang et al., 2023). Conversely, a compulsive need to avoid disappointing others has been found to correlate with depressive symptomatology (Hawley et al., 2006; Nepon et al., 2011). Similarly, the compulsive need to prioritize the needs of others while neglecting one's own has been shown to negatively impact relationships and well-being (Barrocas, 2024; Impett et al., 2005; Lin et al., 2016).

While sharing theoretical similarities with the "disease-prone personality" concepts described by Friedman and Rosenman (Type A/B), Temoshok (Cancer-Prone), and Denollet (Distress-Type), Maté's deliberate use of "behavior patterns" instead of "personality" is critical. It underscores the plausibility of behavioral change as a pathway to improving physical and mental health prioritization, offering a more actionable and less rigid framework than the more enduring construct of "personality" (Maté & Maté, 2022). Maté suggested that these "behavior patterns", compulsive concern for the emotional needs of others, over-identification with work, suppression of anger, and the need never to disappoint anyone, are reinforced in some cultures because society often views them as diligence, compassion, kindness, and generosity (Maté & Maté, 2022). This normalization, Maté argued, leads individuals to overlook the detrimental impact these behaviors can have on their bodies and overall health.

While Maté's framework sheds light on how certain behavior patterns, often praised as virtues, can carry hidden costs. Understanding these dynamics requires placing them within cultural contexts that shape individuals' values and responses. To truly grasp this tension, it's crucial to consider how culture shapes what people see as normal, admirable, or excessive, especially in places like the Philippines, where collective identity and social harmony guide much of daily life. Thus, exploring these dynamics through the lens of Filipino psychology becomes essential.

Culture and Filipino Psychology

The Filipino value system is deeply rooted in collectivism, emphasizing harmonious interpersonal relationships, loyalty, respect for authority, and a strong sense of social responsibility. These Filipino value systems were unmasked when the field of Sikolohiyang Pilipino emerged in the 1970s, scientifically exploring psychology through Filipino experiences (Pe-Pua & Protacio-Marcelino, 2000). Key traits include pakikisama (smooth interpersonal relationships, conformity), hiya (shame, propriety, self-sacrifice), utang na loob (debt of gratitude, reciprocity), and pakikiramdam (avoiding offense, thoughtfulness) (Clemente, 2008; Enriquez, 1963; Lasquety-Reyes, 2016; Pe-Pua & Protacio-Marcelino, 2000; Yacat, 2013). These traits parallel behaviors observed by Maté. However, one compelling question

that ought to be answered is when one draws the line between normal and pathological expressions of kindness and self-sacrifice.

Collectively, these identifiable behavioral patterns are hypothesized to exert a significant influence over key psychological stress markers, including anxiety, depression, and somatic symptom burden. These conditions represent pervasive mental health challenges that profoundly impact quality of life and productivity, particularly within the demanding landscape faced by Cebuano working adults. In the Philippines, recent data from the Department of Health and the World Health Organization indicate that at least 3.6 million Filipinos suffer from mental, neurological, and substance use disorders, with depression and anxiety being among the most common, especially in the working-age population (Buenaventura et al., 2023; Flores et al., 2018; Sugarol, 2023; Tolentino, 2004). This is further exacerbated by observed reluctance among Filipinos to seek formal mental health support despite experiencing considerable psychological distress (Martinez et al., 2020).

Given the increasing recognition of occupational stressors, identifying the underlying behavioral vulnerabilities contributing to these markers is paramount. The Disease-Prone Behavior Patterns conceptualized by Maté (2022) closely mirror core Filipino cultural traits and values such as *pakikisama*, *hiya*, *utang na loob*, and *pakikiramdam*. But where do we draw the line between normal and pathological thoughtfulness and caring? And in the context of *hiya*, where do we draw the line between normal self-sacrifice and pathological self-sacrifice for the sake of other people? Understanding and quantifying these contextually relevant behavior patterns is, therefore, crucial for developing targeted interventions.

In light of this, the present study aimed to achieve two primary objectives (see **Figure 1**). First, it sought to develop and validate a scale measuring disease-prone behavior patterns (DPBP) that capture traits such as compulsive concern for others, over-identification with duties, suppression of healthy anger, and a heightened sense of responsibility for others' emotions. Second, the study tested a hypothesized theoretical framework using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM), integrating both the measurement model (via Confirmatory Factor Analysis) and the structural model (Path Analysis). Through this approach, the research aims to clarify how culturally embedded patterns of behavior may contribute to psychological stress among Cebuano working adults, thereby bridging the gap between cultural values and mental health outcomes.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

Materials and Methods

Participants

This study adopted broad yet clearly defined eligibility criteria to ensure the inclusion of participants with relevant and diverse experiences. Individuals were eligible to participate if they met the following conditions: (a) they were residents of Cebu Province; (b) they were at least 18 years old at the time of data collection; (c) they were currently engaged in regular employment; and (d) they could understand either English or Cebuano. Exclusion criteria included: (a) individuals below 18 years old (minors); (b) pregnant individuals; (c) persons with disabilities (PWDs); and (d) individuals whose occupations did not fall within the defined scope of regular employment (e.g., contractual, piece-rate employment). These criteria were implemented to ensure ethical appropriateness, participant safety, and contextual relevance to the study.

Measures

The study employed three standardized self-report measures and one researcher-developed scale. Anxiety symptomatology was assessed using the 7-item *Generalized Anxiety Disorder Scale (GAD-7)*, which evaluates symptoms over the past two weeks using a 4-point Likert scale (0 = *not at all* to 3 = *nearly every day*). The GAD-7 has demonstrated high internal consistency ($\alpha = .92$) and good construct validity across populations (Spitzer et al., 2006; Swinson, 2006).

Depressive symptomatology was measured using the *Patient Health Questionnaire-2 (PHQ-2)*, a brief 2-item screener for core symptoms of depression (i.e., anhedonia and depressed mood). Items are rated on a 4-point scale (0 to 3), and the PHQ-2 has shown adequate reliability ($\alpha = .83$) and strong predictive utility in clinical settings (Kroenke et al., 2001; Zuthoff et al., 2010).

Somatic burden symptomatology was assessed using the *Somatic Symptom Scale-8 (SSS-8)*, which consists of 8 items covering common physical symptoms (e.g., fatigue, gastrointestinal discomfort, pain), rated on a 5-point scale (0 = *not at all* to 4 = *very much*). The SSS-8 has shown strong internal consistency ($\alpha = .81-.82$) and good convergent validity with related measures (Gierk et al., 2013).

Additionally, a 16-item Disease-Prone Behavior Pattern Scale was developed by the lead researcher to assess maladaptive stress-related behaviors, including emotional suppression, overcommitment, and negative self-appraisal. Items were rated on a 4-point Likert scale (0 = *never* to 4 = *always*).

Procedures

This study was reviewed and approved by the Silliman University Research Ethics Committee (2023-405-*Luspe*), following the National Ethical Guidelines for Health and Health-Related Research (2022). Participants were recruited through convenience sampling, and data were collected using a self-administered questionnaire distributed via online Google Forms to minimize social desirability bias and prevent underreporting on sensitive questions (Harling et al., 2017). Data collection lasted for approximately 3 months (January to March 2024).

Determining the sample size for Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) involves several considerations, including statistical power, the number of indicators, the number of parameters, and overall model complexity (Wolf et al., 2013). For non-normal data, as is often the case in social science research, Nevitt & Hancock (2001) recommend a sample size between 200 and 1,000, while Yuan & Bentler (2000) suggest a minimum of more than 400. Given that the present study did not employ a highly complex model, the target was to gather more than 400 complete responses (i.e., with no missing data).

Preliminary Analyses

A total of 1,134 (Male = 697, Female = 437) responses qualified for data analysis after data cleaning, with participants' age ranging from 18 to 55 years ($M = 29.06$, $SD = 7.88$). Descriptive statistics showed that item means, standard deviations, and univariate skewness and kurtosis values were within acceptable ranges. However, multivariate normality was violated, warranting the use of a robust estimation method for structural equation modeling. Polychoric correlations were computed due to the ordinal nature of the

data (Holgado–Tello et al., 2008). Results indicated acceptable inter-item relationships, with many correlations exceeding $r = .30$. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure indicated excellent sampling adequacy (overall MSA = 0.91), Bartlett’s Test of Sphericity was significant, $\chi^2(120) = 10,351.83$, $p < .001$, and the 16-item Disease-Prone Behavior Pattern Scale (see **Table 1**) demonstrated high internal consistency (Cronbach’s $\alpha = 0.879$) confirming the data’s suitability for factor analysis.

Table 1. Reliability Estimates of the DPBP Scale

Disease – Prone Behavior Pattern (overall Cronbach’s $\alpha = 0.879$)		α if item Deleted
F1	Q1: I worry so much about the welfare of others that I neglect my own welfare.	0.875
	Q5: I worry about the needs of other people so much that I neglect my own needs.	0.871
	Q9: I prioritize the needs of other people over my own.	0.870
	Q13: I focus so much on the emotional needs of others that I neglect my own emotional needs.	0.869
F2	Q2: I think about work-related problems even after my shift or work hours end.	0.872
	Q6: I worry about work even on my rest day or day off.	0.873
	Q10: I spend more time thinking about work problems, sacrificing time meant for myself.	0.868
	Q14: I work even when I'm not feeling well, just to avoid using my sick leave.	0.876
F3	Q3: I hide my anger to avoid conflict.	0.877
	Q7: I keep my anger inside and never show it to anyone.	0.873
	Q11: I hide my anger to the point of feeling heavy inside.	0.869
	Q15: I hide my anger, hoping it will disappear, but it never really does.	0.869
F4	Q4: I try to never disappoint or upset anyone, so I live up to their expectations of me.	0.872
	Q8: I have difficulty saying "NO" to requests and demands because I don't want to disappoint anyone.	0.870
	Q12: I feel responsible for how people feel toward me.	0.870
	Q16: I feel responsible for the problems happening at home.	0.873

Main Data Analysis

Given the non-normality of the data, the Diagonally Weighted Least Squares (DWLS) using a polychoric correlation matrix estimator was utilized in the primary SEM analyses to obtain robust parameter estimates and fit indices suitable for ordinal indicators and continuous variables with non-normal distributions. Literature indicates that this is the optimal procedure when the observed variables in latent variable models are ordinal (DiStefano & Morgan, 2014; Li, 2016).

Using the Lavaan Package in R (*Version 2025.05.1+513*), Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) was employed to examine the hypothesized relationships between disease-prone behavior patterns and psychological stress markers among Cebuano working adults. The measurement model specified a four-factor 2nd-order structure for Disease-Prone Behavior Patterns and a path analysis between Disease-Prone Behavior Patterns and Psychological Stress Markers. Model fit was assessed using multiple indices, including the chi-square statistic, Comparative Fit Index (CFI), Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI), Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) with its 90% confidence interval, and Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR). Standardized parameter estimates and their statistical significance were examined for all factor loadings and the hypothesized structural path.

Results

Results show that the full Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) analysis supported the hypothesized structure and relationships among the study variables. The following sections present the results in sequence, beginning with the measurement properties assessed through Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA), followed by the structural relationships evaluated via path analysis, and concluding with the overall model fit and interpretation of the complete SEM.

Table 2. Factor Loadings of the Measurement Model

Disease – Prone Behavior Pattern (DPBP)		Factor Loadings (Q → F) (λ)	Path Coefficients (F → DPBP) (β)
F1 <i>Compulsive concern for others' emotional needs at the expense of one's own</i>	Q1	0.676	0.774
	Q5	0.803	
	Q9	0.816	
	Q13	0.797	
F2 <i>Over-identification with duties and responsibilities</i>	Q2	0.814	0.672
	Q6	0.815	
	Q10	0.841	
	Q14	0.613	
F3 <i>Suppression of healthy anger</i>	Q3	0.688	0.718
	Q7	0.779	
	Q11	0.849	
	Q15	0.846	
F4 <i>Perceived responsibility for others' feelings and the need to avoid disappointing anyone</i>	Q4	0.649	0.966
	Q8	0.717	
	Q12	0.717	
	Q16	0.605	

Measurement Model (Confirmatory Factor Analysis)

Table 2 above shows the standardized factor loadings (λ), which represent the strength of the relationship between observed items (Q1 to Q16) and their respective latent constructs (F1 – F4). For Factor 1 (F1), loadings range from 0.676 to 0.816. For Factor 2 (F2), the range is 0.613 to 0.841. Factor 3 (F3) shows loadings between 0.688 and 0.849, while Factor 4 (F4) ranges from 0.605 to 0.717. These values suggest that the items reliably measured their respective latent traits. Moreover, the path coefficients (β), which reflect the strength of the relationships between each first-order trait (F1-F4) and the second-order construct (DPBP), were all statistically significant: F1 (β = .774, p < .001), F2 (β = .672, p < .001), F3 (β = .718, p < .001), and F4 (β = .966, p < .001). These coefficients indicate that all four traits substantially contribute to the higher-order construct, with F4 exerting the strongest influence on DPBP.

Structural Model (Path Analysis)

Figure 2 below shows the latent construct Disease-Prone Behavior Pattern (DPBP) emerged as a significant predictor of Psychological Stress Markers (PSYCH) as indicated by anxiety symptomatology (GAD-7), depressive symptomatology (PHQ-9), and somatic burden symptomatology (SSS-8). Specifically, the direct effect of DPBP on PSYCH was substantial, with a standardized regression coefficient of β = .455, p < .001. This indicates that participants reporting higher levels of disease-prone behaviors also reported significantly greater psychological stress. The model revealed that DPBP accounted for 20.7% of the variance in Psychological Stress Markers (R² = .207).

Figure 2. Path Analysis, DPBP predicting PSYCH

Testing the Hypothesized Theoretical Framework

The overall hypothesized model exhibited an excellent fit to the observed data, as evidenced by robust fit indices: $\chi^2(147) = 745.478$, $p < .001$; Comparative Fit Index (CFI) = .980; Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI) = .980; Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) = .055; and Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR) = .060. Collectively, these values meet or exceed conventional thresholds for good model fit (see Table 2, Hooper et al., 2008; Hu & Bentler, 1999), indicating that the specified model provides a statistically adequate and theoretically meaningful representation of the proposed model structure. The comprehensive structural equation model is depicted in Figure 3.

Table 2. Fit Indices Criteria based on Hu and Bentler (1999)

Excellent Fit	Acceptable fit	Hypothesized Model
CFI: >0.95	0.90 – 0.94	0.984
TLI: >0.95	0.90 – 0.94	0.981
RMSEA: <0.05	0.05 – 0.08	0.060 [0056 – 0.064]
SRMR: <0.05	0.05 – 0.08	0.055

Figure 3. Full Structural Equation Model of the Hypothesized Model

Discussion

The results of the structural equation modeling provide empirical support for the conceptual linkage between disease-prone behavioral tendencies and heightened psychological stress among the target research participants. Participants who demonstrated habitual self-neglect, via emotional suppression, excessive duty adherence, and interpersonal over-responsibility, reported significantly greater levels of anxiety, depression, and somatic symptom burden. This aligns with Gabor Maté's theoretical framework of "disease-prone personalities," where chronic self-sacrifice, emotional repression, and hyper-responsibility are central behavioral themes associated with deteriorating mental and physical health.

Among the four behavioral traits assessed, **F4**, a perceived responsibility for others' feelings and a deep-seated fear of disappointing others, emerged as the strongest contributor to the disease-prone profile ($\beta = .966$). This finding emphasizes how internalized relational expectations, especially those rooted in cultural and familial norms, may serve as critical psychological vulnerabilities. The elevated influence of

F2 (over-identification with responsibilities) and **F3** (suppressed anger) further illustrates the psychosomatic toll of rigid self-control and perfectionistic striving. While **F1** (compulsive concern for others' emotional needs) also significantly contributed to the DPBP, its influence was comparatively lower, suggesting a nuanced interplay of these traits.

Attachment vs. Authenticity, and Culture

Maté argued that when the need for attachment is in direct conflict with the need for authenticity, attachment invariably takes precedence. In some cultures (e.g., collectivist cultures) where family obligations are heavily emphasized, this often means prioritizing the expectations and needs of one's family over one's sense of truth and individuality. Such prioritization serves to preserve group cohesion, which historically has been vital for survival. The significance of this dynamic lies in how culturally reinforced behavior patterns, though potentially pathological, are often mischaracterized as admirable strengths. Traits such as excessive self-sacrifice, emotional suppression, and over-responsibility are glorified under labels like compassion, diligence, generosity, and kindness.

In addition, these behavioral tendencies must be interpreted within the broader Filipino cultural context. The study's findings closely parallel traditional Filipino values such as *pakikisama* (harmony in social relations), *hiya* (shame, propriety), *utang na loob* (reciprocity and gratitude), and *pakikiramdam* (sensitivity to others), which form the cultural foundations of Filipino relational life (Clemente, 2008; Enriquez, 1963; Lasquetey-Reyes, 2016; Pe-Pua & Protacio-Marcelino, 2000; Yacat, 2013).

In essence, these culturally "normalized" traits, while socially adaptive in many respects, can also condition individuals to suppress their emotional needs, maintain peace at personal cost, and internalize guilt or shame when unable to meet relational expectations, leading to the emergence of stress-prone patterns, heightening vulnerability to psychological distress. These parallels raise crucial questions about the fine line between culturally normative expressions of kindness and self-sacrifice, and their potential to become pathological when enacted compulsively or at significant personal cost, as suggested by Maté (2022).

The findings of this study suggest that these culturally ingrained behavioral patterns, when manifesting as disease-prone behaviors, may serve as a significant pathway to heightened psychological stress for Cebuano working adults. The continuous prioritization of others' needs, the suppression of personal emotions (like anger), and the pervasive need to avoid disappointing others can accumulate into chronic internal stress. Compounded by the reluctance to seek formal mental health support due to stigma or cultural norms, individuals may lack adequate outlets to process their distress, leading to the exacerbation of anxiety, depression, and somatic symptoms. Understanding the complex interplay between cultural values, specific behavioral patterns, and mental health outcomes is crucial for developing culturally sensitive interventions that promote healthier coping mechanisms and encourage timely help-seeking behaviors within the Filipino context.

Conclusion

This study provides compelling evidence that culturally rooted behavior patterns, particularly those characterized by excessive emotional responsibility, duty-driven self-neglect, suppressed anger, and an ingrained fear of disappointing others, are significantly associated with psychological stress among Cebuano working adults. The findings validate the conceptual premise of disease-prone behavioral profiles as meaningful predictors of anxiety, depression, and somatic symptom burden.

Importantly, the results underscore that what may traditionally be considered virtues within the Filipino cultural context, selflessness, harmony, and relational loyalty, can, when rigidly internalized, evolve into psychosocial liabilities. This nuanced interplay between culture and psychopathology highlights the need for mental health frameworks in the Philippines to adopt both culturally sensitive and behaviorally specific approaches to prevention and intervention.

In conclusion, the psychological toll of chronic self-neglect and emotional over-responsibility, especially within collectivist cultures, must be recognized as a public mental health priority. By integrating insights from both Western models and indigenous Filipino psychology, this research advocates for a more holistic and culturally anchored understanding of mental health risk among Filipino adults.

Limitations and Future Directions

While this study offers valuable insights, it is important to acknowledge certain limitations. As a cross-sectional study, causality cannot be directly inferred from the identified relationships. Future longitudinal studies are needed to establish the predictive nature of Disease-Prone Behavior Patterns on psychological stress over time. Additionally, the reliance on self-report measures, though common in psychological research, may be subject to response biases. Future research could explore the integration of objective measures or informant reports to complement self-reported data. Given the convenience sampling method, the generalizability of these findings to the broader Filipino working adult population should be considered with caution. Future studies could employ more rigorous sampling strategies to enhance external validity. Finally, further qualitative research could delve deeper into the lived experiences of Filipino working adults to better understand how cultural values manifest as disease-prone behaviors and their specific impact on mental well-being. Examining the mediating or moderating roles of other psychological constructs (e.g., resilience, social support) within this framework would also be a fruitful avenue for future research.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest regarding this research. Raw data is available upon request.

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